

ON ORGANO-ARSENICAL COMPOUNDS. PART V

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Some diamidine derivatives of the types (III and IV), containing arsenious acid group, have been synthesised

It has been shown by Ashley *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 103) that the aromatic symmetrical diamidines have outstanding antiparasitic properties against protozoa. It is not known whether such activity depends specifically on the amidine group which may function by assisting adsorption, through the resonance of its ion, or by interfering with a similarly constituted metabolite in the parasite (cf. Albert *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1947, 1452). It is also known that certain arsenic derivatives have a beneficial effect on patients suffering from various forms of trypanosomiasis. Whether the presence of both arsenic and amidino groups in one molecule will stimulate, or suppress, such action has still to be determined. With this object in view, it has been considered desirable to synthesise some diamidines containing arsenious acid group.

In parts III and IV (Pathak and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 254, 293) of this series of papers, it has been shown that *N*-alkylated amidines containing arsenious acid group are obtained by reacting acetanilide or its derivatives with *p*-arsanilic acid in presence of phosphorus oxychloride. *p*-Cyanacetanilide has now been reacted with *p*-arsanilic acid in presence of phosphorus oxychloride to yield a mixture of the acetamidine derivative (I) and a compound (m.p. 182-84°) containing chlorine but no arsenic, the constitution of which could not be definitely ascertained. Similarly, the condensation of *p*-cyanobenzanilide with *p*-arsanilic acid in presence of phosphorus oxychloride has furnished a mixture of the benzamidine derivative (II) and a non-arsenical chloro compound (m.p. 190-92°) of undetermined constitution.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

Attempts were made to prepare the imino-ether hydrochlorides of the above cyano compounds (I and II), containing strong basic groups, in ether, benzene or chloroform but in each case passing of dry hydrogen chloride caused immediate formation and precipitation of the cyano hydrochlorides. The problem has been, however, solved by

the discovery that nitrobenzene (cf. Ashley *et al.*, *loc. cit.*; U. S. P., 2,204, 983; B. P. 510,097) is an excellent solvent for these cyano hydrochlorides and also for the resulting imino-ether hydrochlorides, the latter having been almost quantitatively precipitated by the addition of ether. The imino-ether hydrochlorides, thus obtained, have easily furnished the arsenious acid derivatives (III and IV), both of which contain an unsubstituted and a substituted amidino group. These compounds (III and IV) readily respond to the specific colour reaction as discovered by Fuller (*Nature*, 1944, 164, 773) for unsubstituted aromatic amidines.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

(*Phenyl-4-cyano*)-(phenyl-4-arsenious acid)-acetamidine (I).—An intimate mixture of *p*-cyanoacetanilide (16 g., prepared according to the method of Bogoslovskii, *J. Gen. Chem.*, U. S. S. R., 1938, 1, 1784) and *p*-arsanilic acid (21.7 g.) was gradually added to phosphorus oxychloride (90 c.c.) and the mixture was then heated in an oil-bath at 125°–130° for 5 hours. Next day, the reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice, when on stirring a pasty mass was obtained. The supernatant liquid was decanted and basified with ammonium hydroxide, when a solid was precipitated. This solid was mixed with the above pasty mass and the total quantity was then triturated with 5% caustic soda solution and finally filtered.

The alkaline filtrate was treated with charcoal, filtered and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The acidic solution, when basified with ammonium hydroxide, precipitated a cream-colored solid which is soluble in alcohol and in acetic acid. It could not be induced to crystallise from any of these solvents and was therefore purified by dissolving in 5% caustic soda solution, acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid and finally treatment with excess of ammonium hydroxide. The solid (7 g.), when dried *in vacuo*, begins to shrink and soften at 200° and melts at 210° to a viscous mass. (Found: As, 21.45; N, 11.9. $C_{15}H_{14}O_2N_3As$ requires As, 21.84; N, 12.24 per cent). It is readily soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid and in dilute alkali but insoluble in aqueous ammonia or bicarbonate. Its acetic acid solution readily decolorises iodine solution. From its solution in 10% caustic soda solution it is precipitated as such when saturated with sodium chloride. The same compound (I) has been obtained by reacting *p*-aminophenylarsenoxide with *p*-cyanoacetanilide in presence of phosphorus oxychloride under identical conditions, which shows conclusively that (I) is an arsenious acid derivative and not an arsonic acid.

The alkali-insoluble solid was crystallised twice from alcohol in cream-colored needles (6.5 g.), m.p. 182–84°. The constitution of this compound, which contains chlorine but no arsenic, could not be definitely ascertained.

(*Phenyl*)-(phenyl-4-arsenious acid)-*p*-cyanobenzamidine (II). — *p*-Cyanobenzanilide has been prepared by reacting *p*-cyanobenzoyl chloride (Ashley *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) with aniline. It melts at 178–79° (cf. Fischer and Wolter, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1909, ii, 80, 102).

The method of condensation of *p*-cyanobenzanilide with *p*-arsanilic acid and that of isolation of the reaction products were the same as described above. The light yellow solid (compound II), which is readily soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid and in dilute alkali but insoluble in aqueous ammonia or bicarbonate, shrinks at 220° and melts

to a viscous mass at 270°. (Found: As, 17.87. $C_{20}H_{16}O_2N_2As$ requires As, 18.49 per cent).

The alkali-insoluble solid was found to be a crude hydrochloride. The free base was obtained by dissolving the hydrochloride in boiling water and treating the solution with alkali, when a brownish solid was precipitated. It was crystallised from alcohol in cream-colored rectangular plates, m.p. 190-92°. The constitution of this compound, which contains chlorine but no arsenic and furnishes, when treated with alcoholic hydrochloric acid, a hydrochloride (m.p. 320-22°), could not be definitely ascertained.

(*Phenyl-4-amidino*)-(phenyl-4-arsenious acid)-acetamidine (III).— A solution of the compound (I, 5 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (100 c.c.) was saturated at 0° with dry hydrochloric acid gas and the resulting solution was then kept in a closed vessel in the refrigerator for 6 days with occasional shaking. The imino-ether hydrochloride was then precipitated by addition of dry ether (400 c.c.), filtered, washed with dry ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator. It was treated with 15% alcoholic ammonia (50 c.c.) and the mixture was heated in a closed vessel at 110°-115° for 5 hours. After cooling overnight, the almost colorless precipitate, which was found to consist mainly of ammonium chloride, was filtered and the filtrate distilled under reduced pressure to remove as much of alcohol as possible. The residue was treated with ammonium hydroxide, when a solid was obtained. It could not be induced to crystallise from alcohol or any other organic solvent and was purified by solution in cold dilute alkali, acidification under cooling with dilute hydrochloric acid and finally treatment with excess of ammonium hydroxide. The brownish solid (2.8 g.), which was dried *in vacuo*, softens at 240° and melts at 250° to a viscous mass. (Found: As, 20.12; N, 15.18. $C_{18}H_{17}O_2N_4As$ requires As, 20.81; N, 15.56 per cent).

(*Phenyl*)-(phenyl-4-arsenious acid)-p-amidinobenzamidine (IV).— The method of preparation was the same as described above. The light yellow solid melts to a viscous mass at 302°. (Found: N, 12.94. $C_{20}H_{18}O_2N_4As$ requires N, 13.27 per cent).

(4:4'-*Diamidinodiphenyl*)-(4:4'-arsenophenyl)-acetamidine (V).— A solution of the compound (III, 1 g.) in the requisite quantity of 5% hydrochloric acid was reduced by adding, with stirring, 35% hypophosphorous acid (8 c.c.) and 1 c.c. of 1% aqueous solution of potassium iodide. Soon the solution became turbid and a precipitate was formed. The reaction mixture, after being occasionally stirred at room temperature for about 3 hours, was triturated with excess of 10% cold caustic soda solution. The resulting light brown solid was filtered, again triturated with 10% caustic soda solution, filtered, washed thoroughly with water till free from chloride and dried *in vacuo*. It melts at 256-58° (decomp.). (Found: As, 22.3. $C_{20}H_{20}N_4As_2$ requires As, 22.9 per cent).